

CONTENT AND CHARACTER OF SPIRITUAL VALUES

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Annotation. The article provides feedback on the factors that influence the system of spiritual values on it. It has been studied that transformational processes in the world of spiritual values continue today but not all of them can be positively evaluated. It has been analyzed that certain socio-economic and political factors negatively affect the nature of spiritual values, their social position.

Keywords: Spirituality, spiritual culture, spiritual value, political value, legal value, social attitude, reform.

Spiritual values change under the influence of social conditions, processes, and are able to find evolution. It is for this reason that the updates that took place in Uzbekistan during the years of independence in the socio-economic, political and spiritual-cultural spheres of society radically changed the content and composition of spiritual values. The new social situation, large-scale reforms, on the one hand, significantly enriched, improved the spiritual values that have been decided over the centuries. On the second hand, under the influence of social processes, the composition of spiritual values radically changed: on the basis of traditional spiritual values, new ones appeared, and some were devalued. On the third hand, there were updates in the hierarchy of spiritual values, some of which became more valued and others relatively less valued. In the following years, due to the height of efforts to establish a new Uzbekistan, changes in the content and composition of spiritual values became more intensive. Therefore, today's spiritual value system of Uzbekistan is significantly different not only from the one that prevailed in the past, but also from the one that was decided in Soviet times. When we analyze these changes in detail.

The first factor that changed the content of spiritual values became associated with political reforms. As you know, political reform refers to changes aimed at modernizing the system of Public Administration by improving the activities of political institutions and updating the content of political relations. The main goal of political reforms is to strengthen democracy, protect the rights and freedoms of citizens, increase the efficiency and responsibility of state

bodies. Political reform is not a process that is carried out on the basis of a voluntaristic approach, based on the Will and desires of narrow circles. It assumes, first of all, the existence of a social necessity for radical political change. Second, political reform requires certain social conditions.

In the early years of independence in Uzbekistan, both such social necessity and social conditions were ripe. On the one hand, the outdated political system of Soviet reality had already ceased to serve the interests of society – a situation that exaggerated the need to reform the political system of society. On the second hand, the high confidence of the people in the state, the size of the potential for reforms, the presence of solidarity among social groups created conditions for the realization of political updates. Due to this social necessity and conditions, in the early years of independence, the foundations of new Uzbek statehood were created, the activities of political institutions of society were discovered, the content of political relations was dramatically changed.

But at the initial stage of political reform, the principle of “State – Society – man” was followed. The construction and management of the state, all political structures, their style of work and activities were also formed on this principle . It was not until the following years that political reforms were subjected to a special principle. In this regard, the president of the country wrote: “a person, his rights and happiness should be the highest priority goal of public policy, the activities of all state bodies. It is darcor that the construction of society and public policy should rely on this idea and be organized on the principle of “State – for Man”. During the political reforms carried out on this principle, not only the system of Public Administration and the character of political relations changed, but a completely new political space was created in society.

To operate in a new political space, it will be necessary to rely on new political knowledge, norms and principles. This necessity devalued the political knowledge formed in Uzbekistan from the point of view of communist ideology, led to the fact that political knowledge of the political being of a democratic society took their place. This knowledge today allows citizens of the country to draw reasoned conclusions about political processes, effectively operate in social life, wisely exercise their political rights. The nationwide referendum held in 2023 and the presidential elections of the Republic of Uzbekistan demonstrated this.

The second factor that changed the content of spiritual values became associated with the modernization of the legal system. In scientific sources, the legal system

of society is defined as a set of legal norms, spheres and institutions that regulate various relations in it. This system determines the procedure for resolving disputes and punishing violations of the rights and obligations of citizens, the activities of government agencies and organizations . The character and effectiveness of social processes in the country, especially the success of the reforms being carried out, the rule of law, the application of the ideas of appreciation of human rights to hayo, directly depends on the level of perfection of the legal system.

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